

An Empirical Study on TQM Practices and its impact on Organizations in India

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Abstract

Achieving customer satisfaction is the most important objective of the organizations and total quality management is the most effective approach to achieve this objective. TQM is a quintessence of concepts, methods and applications. TQM is an effective method which has an ability to transform the organizational performance by reaping the real benefits from it. Indian organizations have to come to understand that, in order to stay competitive, an improvement in organizational quality performance is necessary. This study focusses mainly on the benefits that companies derived from implementing this techniques. This study was observed only on the selected companies based on their perceived quality performance.

Keywords: quality, TQM, techniques.....

Introduction

TQM is omnipotent and spread its wings across every sphere of the global corporate world. Companies in the current scenario faces incredible pressures to improve the quality of their products because of the frequent changes in the customer's tastes and preferences. It's not just addressing the demand alone but also the cost involved in the process on improvement. Motto of the business in now is on adding value to the customers. How the value can be added offering all what the customer prefer from the existing product without increasing the price?

There are various reasons for the companies of India to implement TQM as it is a driving force to face the competitive world. This research paper stresses on the evolution and feast of TQM in India and it also further categorises the sources for poor quality of products and services. For a company to remain competitive, quality must remain a priority. Later a critical view of the quality scene in India is presented. It is concluded that Indian companies have a long way to be accepted for their products at International level.

A robust guarantee to superiority, and consumer contentment programs are indispensable to participate both smaller and larger

entrant. TQM denotes to the quest for eminence that encompasses every Tom, Dick, and Harry in the organization. TQM assimilates the whole association in a persistent struggle to improve quality and customer satisfaction. TQM always believe that the people committed to the job knows what is wrong and how to fix it. This approach on the whole represents customer satisfaction involving customers, people and the continuous improvement of the processes. Hence, the overall primary objective of TQM is achieving customer satisfaction by involving customers.

Need for the Study

This study aims to examine the impact of TQM execution on managerial performance which is a very important note in the measurement of an organization. This study throws research aspect which examines the relationship between implementation of quality management and competitive positioning. The properties of quality administration, operative assignation, unremitting enhancement and customer's satisfaction were observed in the study. The impact of quality management practices on firms' performance is the matter of interest and challenges among researchers. This study brings out the benefits of implementing TQM with the live examples from Indian companies and prove that the country is feasible to adapt these techniques for the success.

Scope of the Study

TQM requires a high level of promise for instigating TQM in all characteristics of an organization. Top management must create an environment where the TQM is owned and nurtured by employees. One of the key aspect of the TQM is to create high level of customer and manufacture and supply right quantity of products and services at right in time at affordable cost. TQM helps in adopting supplier participation for continuous improvement in one end and customer satisfaction in the other end. The scope of this study is to understand, how TQM is incorporated in the organization by creating process focus and culture of organization learning.

Objective of the Study

Objective of the study is to understand;

1. The method of guidance assumed to advance the collaboration of all associates of the company.
2. The unremitting commercial re-engineering where every member becomes his own quality manager.
3. The organizational performance as measured against its proposed yield.
4. The operational efficiency in adaptation processing with respect to unit cost, quality, delivery, litheness and speed of new product introduction.

Review of Literature

A academic in the quality writings can experience bewilderment in the connotation of TQM and the modifications between Total Quality Management and quality- associated happenings such as quality promise, quality rheostat and quality supervision. This misperception hints, in many cases, to the use of these terminologies interchangeably. Therefore, it is very important to have a clear definition and understanding of each of these concepts.

Ahire also developed a model using similar techniques of Black and Porter, to provide ten constructs of TQM. They defined these "constructs" as latent variables, which cannot be measured directly. However, critical factors or constructs can be measured indirectly from their manifestations. For example, customer focus is a critical factor that cannot be measured directly and when a company is customer-focused, manufacturing managers will be aware of the results of

customer satisfaction surveys. Thus, manufacturing managers being aware of customer satisfaction surveys can be one of the manifestations of the critical factor customer focus. Studies also reflects that several frameworks have defined these critical factors/constructs as “TQM elements” and “TQM measures”.

Research Design

It’s a descriptive study where the selected companies were observed based on their known innovative strategies practised at their operational level with higher market share. This also considers the companies that recognises and decreases the mistakes in all operating areas, taking preventive steps, avoids wastes, reduces lead time and easily captures and addresses the customers’ need.

Limitations

1. It’s only an observational study and inferences are made from the information available in the company website, magazines and research journals.
2. This study is not quantitative and inferences are subject to errors.

Methods of TQM

The Total Quality Management element approach

The Total Quality Management component style takes key professional procedures and/or directorial pieces and routines the trappings of quality management to substitute enhancements. This mode was comprehensively castoff in the initial 1980s as corporations strained to gadget parts of TQM as they erudite them.

The Expert Opinion or Guru Approach in the Total Quality Management

The expert assertiveness practises the wisdoms and literatures of unique or supplementary of the chief quality intellectuals as a chaperon against which to govern and where the organization has insufficiencies. Then, the business makes applicable variations to remedy those deficiencies.

For example, executives power in learning Deming’s 14 points or absorb from management consultants where later they would implement what they learnt under this approach.

The Empirical Learning or Organizational model approach in TQM-

In this method, personages or groups visit establishments that have engaged a governance part in Total Quality Management and control their practises and motives on behalf of conquest. Later they assimilate such philosophies on their own notions to develop a managerial prototype reformed for their precise organization.

This method was used broadly in the late 1980s and is illustrated by the preliminary beneficiaries of the Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award.

The Japanese Total Quality approach

Organizations using the Japanese total quality methodology scrutinise the comprehensive execution procedures and approaches labouring by Deming Prize-winning corporations and custom this knowledge to advance a long-range dominant plan for in-house use.

This approach was used by Florida Power and Light—among others—to instrument TQM and to participate for and win the Deming Prize.

Source: CEOpedia

The Award Criteria Approach or Motivational Technique Approach

When using this archetypal, an organization uses the principles of a quality award, for example, the Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award, European Quality Award, the Deming Prize, or to recognize capacities for perfection. Under this approach, TQM implementation concentrates on meeting specific award criteria.

Though some debate that this is not a proper use of award criteria, particular officialdoms do practise this slant and it can upshot in improvement.

1. Achievements of Many Accolades through TQM in TVS Motor Company-

TVS Group is one of the reputed groups of companies known for its traditional and ethical management practises. This group consists of other companies namely Sundaram Fasteners located in Madurai, Lucas TVS, Brakes India and Wheels India located in Chennai, along with Sundaram Break Linings, TVS Motor Company and TVS Electronics.

These group of companies made a mark in the Indian and global markets with their skill to distribute goods of right value, at the right worth and at the right stint. The success mantra of this is its attitude on quality and service.

- The company acknowledged Deming Prize in the year 2002 for their excellent
- Ministry of Science, Government of India gave away the Technology Award in the year 2002 for the commercialization of aboriginal technology for TVS Victor.
- Japan Institute of Plant Maintenance (JIPM) gave the First Category TPM Excellence Award to TVS Group.
- It also received Asian Network for Quality Award in the year 2004.
- “Outstanding Design Excellence Award” was given to TVS Scooty Pep by Business World and National Institute of Design.

Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FEMA), Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) cycle are some of the techniques that are widely followed by this company. 5'S (Seiri, Seiton, Seiso, Seiketsu, Shitsuke) and Kaizen which is a Japanese business thinking of continuous improvement of operative practices are also being practiced extensively in TVS. Quality Function Deployment (QFD) helps the company to overcome sprints in their quality decision making.

Source: Lucas TVS

Building employee participation is yet another success of the TVS. Employees of the TVS are actively encouraged to be a member of Quality Control Circle who meet periodically for the improvement and quality enhancement. Just-in-time for the measures in controlling the cost on inventories, Quality Audit for the interrupted check on quality adherence and flow chart are also practiced as part of Total Productivity Maintenance.

2. Total Quality Management Practises in Rane Limited

The Rane Group, in the middle of the firstborn and the most powerful cluster in the locomotive constituent industry was originated over six spans ago. In 1929, it commenced unassumingly as “Rane Private Limited” dealing with the automobile components and parts.

All engineering progressions are wholly recognised with respect to bureaucratic directions. These help the employees to avoid the most cumbersome situation at work site. Following are some of the steps adhered in this method.

1. Clear explanation on starting the machines are instructed to all the employees. Employees should follow these instructions at the production site.
2. Instructions on how to set the job is indicated with self-understanding pictures.
3. Warnings on how to handle the processes are given in this stage. This explains the parameter and tools to be used for the given processes.
4. Explanations on how to check with what gauges and instruments are quite self-explaining.
5. Safety instructions and safety measures to avoid accidents at the productions site are strictly instigated.

Source: Rane ltd.

After executing TQM, this company has attained an upsurge in customer contentment. This company is known for the on-time delivery. Accomplishing solidarity has also been cited as a advantage of TQM by all the appellants. Perceptibly as a consequence of the employment of TQM quality enhancement has been comprehended as approved by all the defendants. Perfection in yield is another foremost triumph of the company as a outcome of TQM. Surge in cost-effectiveness and improvement in morale are also momentous successes.

3. Growth of Toyota Motor Ltd after World War II

Growing from the vestiges of manufacturing turmoil in post-war Japan, Toyota has become the prime automobile industrialist with over 43% market share. In 1950's Toyota instigated to mark in-roads into overseas marketplaces because of the edge in production practices it made. The paramount Crown mock-ups reached the United States of America with models such as the Corolla, Toyota activated to dimension its status and deals to contending those of inland manufacturers. Toyota started its imports to Europe in 1963 by means of Denmark. Toyota had non-stop growth in Europe's well-educated, sophisticated and complex market. In the year 2000, the company transported its ten millionth car to a patron in Germany.

Employment of Total Quality Management in this establishment had such simplifying influences as top management obligation and engrossment, evolving member participation, employee authorisation, educating communiqué between management and labour, co-ordination in improving quality, collaboration, snowballing patron alignment, detecting customer chucks and desires, uncontrolled retort to customer necessities and positioning to improving productivity. These influences are approved by all perpetrators unambiguously as implementers.

Source : The Economist

During the application of TQM the company cast-off innumerable quality procedures and agendas and discussion which had positive effects on improving their product quality and teams work regularly to correct problems.

Source: Toyato (Evaluation by Deming Prize Committee)

The purpose of cultivating employee obligation is to inspire personnel to make additional assistances to the victory of the firm. Total Quality Management decisively trusts that employees are the foremost basis of asset for the business. The anthropological possessions in this company try to find to create a communal values where principles such as “Continuous Improvement” and “Respect for People” are wholly replicated in all definite commercial and specific doings. The company proceeds determined overhaul to certify stability of employment and attempts to mend working environments.

Conclusion

Bearing in cognizance the contemporary state of international antagonism, it is authoritarian for Indian commerce to ripen a customer-focused ethos as early as possible. This will empower them to exploit their means more resourcefully and effectually for the products or services which the customer wants and is willing to compensate a premium for. This brashness lead to the total quality culture. This requires a complete understanding of the TQM thinking by the senior executives of organization without which accomplishment of the results would not be possible.

Beholding at the know-how of establishments both home-grown and intercontinental with an efficacious enactment of TQM yielded expressively recovering grades in all the performance categories of financial results, customer satisfaction and employee satisfaction. As the scope is coast-to-coast, everyone right from the single employee within the organization- from the meekest to the furthestmost commanding is crucial in order to develop proprietorship of the principles and curtail skirmish of interest.

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